

POTENTIAL FOR SURPRISE

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“ARCHITECTS. All idiots: they always forget to put in the stairs.”
– Bouvard et Pécuchet via Gustave Flaubert,
Dictionary of Accepted Ideas, c.1870s.

This article uses various meanings of the word “projection” to generate a series of interpretations of a particular architectural project (Figs. 01, 06). The project under discussion is a structure constructed of cable ties, hereafter CT_mesh. It was completed in 2011. The geometry of CT_mesh has self-intersecting topology and its surface is made from a continually differentiated pattern (Fig. 02). By now, computational tools for defining such patterns are becoming common and their outcomes recognisable. Consequently, this paper does not attempt to argue that this structure is original as an object but instead discusses it as a material manifestation of some peculiar processes. One such process unfolds at the temporal scale of a design project; in this case, over several weeks. It is concerned with the management of control within what most people would recognise as designing. The very idea of such management is novel within the field of architecture and the paper describes its – also innovative – implementation as layering of heterogeneous constraints. This description positions designing not as a goal-directed demonstration of pre-accumulated expertise but as a deliberate balancing act between composition and improvisation. The other process occurs at a larger temporal scale that can span multiple projects and even encompass disciplinary paradigm shifts. To illustrate, the modest experiment with the layered control mentioned above is motivated by the long-term research into biologically-inspired structures, processes and systems that are characterised by multi-layer hierarchies capable of opportunistic and non-destructive local adjustments.

In relationship to this line of investigation, the examples of thinking discussed in this paper are significant as prototypes that begin to theorise future design and construction workflows that are – like those found in nature – flexibly adaptive to the inherently dynamic environmental conditions.

To use a somewhat clumsy term, such designing-and-making workflows can be described as having greater “innovability,”¹ and this article seeks to contribute to the discussion on what might maximise this property. This inquiry is important because, at least in the experience of the author, the pursuit of innovability does not have universal or intuitive solutions.

One contradiction that is tackled below occurs between standardisation and creativity. It is possible to argue that the accrual of technical knowledge depends on standardisation, compartmentalisation and reuse. For example, the sharing of knowledge through democratised tools including standardised means of electronic communication, common data structures (e.g., polygonal meshes), fixed file types (e.g., STL or IGES) and universal machine-instruction languages (G-Code) has been credited for the continuing wave of innovation in software and the predicted “fabrication revolution.”² In parallel with such general trends, architectural design also becomes increasingly dependent on reusable structures such as data types, operators and expressions, algorithms and dataflow programming. File standards, programming libraries and databases of components are becoming progressively more important for efficiency, collaboration and performance-oriented designing.

Opposite:

Fig 01. A full view of the CT_mesh structure, suspended. Note the varying densities and transitions between more and less regular patterns. See a detailed example of this in Fig. 02 and the contrasting smoothness of source geometry in Fig. 03. All photographs by the author.

The growing use of parametric models is a common example. An important motivation for parametric workflows is their support for remodelling and reuse. As Volker Mueller comments, such models allow designers to explore entire solution spaces, instead of building single solutions.³ Construction and exploration of such spaces requires explicit representations of ideas that are usually otherwise treated intuitively and this challenge has the potential to usefully expand the intellectual scope of designing.⁴

However, as a response to the wickedness that is typical of design challenges, can this need for explicitness be a hindrance to creativity? Can the emphasis on controlled outcomes and pre-imposed solutions-space boundaries inherent in parametric modelling preclude or discourage innovation? And more generally, does the orientation towards the past work encapsulated in computational ontologies, objects, structures and procedures diminish designers' capabilities for managing change in a complex, dynamic and unpredictable world?

Interest in such concepts as volatility or emergence exemplify work that seeks to make the outcomes of architectural computing more open.⁵ For example, form-finding techniques are praised for their capability to improve explorations of solution and possibility spaces. Feedback-based approaches and complex dynamic systems are valued for modelling behaviours that are intrinsically unpredictable or too complex for top-down control. Creative practices in other disciplines have also developed resistance to conventions, standards and recipes in the form of tactics for embracing change, disruption, and chance. In this context, volatility, spontaneity, improvisation, heuristics, stochastics and randomness become appreciable as productive design behaviours – behaviours that can increase innovability or, in other words, accept, expect and cultivate surprise.

Fig 02. Subdivision meshes at three levels of complexity. Note the regularity of patterns, compared with Fig. 01.

1. Projections

I will do projection in thy presence, my son – in thy very presence, – and thine eyes shall witness the truth.

– Walter Scott, Kenilworth II, 1821

In English, the word projection has more than 20 distinct meanings. It is possible to see these meanings as related to some common source. For example, they can be unified around a notion of movement from an origin, such as that provided by the Latin meaning of throwing forth or away. More inclusively, one can see these meanings as signposts of expanding intellectual worlds. For example, such expansion is evident in the senses related to geometry, mathematics, physics, cartography and crystallography: from Hipparchus with his infinite rays and orthographic projections, to transposition of any figure to any surface, to any mode of construction founded on some definite geometrical principle, to projections as homomorphisms, or mappings between abstract algebraic structures and so on. More inclusively still, and with some less intuitive results, it is also possible to see the pattern of existing meanings as a space explored by complex, historically, geographically and culturally situated practices that mix logic with idiosyncratic subjectivity and imaginative misapplication. Below are some of the meanings of the word projection, used to think about such procedures...

1.1 Extension

Do but observe the Projection of the Hip; besides, the Bloom upon the Face; 'tis a Female beyond all Contradiction

– John Gay, *Three Hours after Marriage: A Comedy, as It Is Acted at the Theatre Royal*, 1717

Projection can mean an object that extends from another, such as a formation of rock that successfully resists gravity or an architectural structure. The structure discussed in this article was assembled to explore issues of spontaneity and control in relationship to digital tools. This exploration was conducted through the making of an installation, titled CT_mesh, that was about 4 metres long and consisted of approximately 20,000 cable ties arranged into a complex surface (Figs. 01, 02 and 06). The patterning of CT_mesh was made from loops of varying sizes (Fig. 04). As is common in parametric approaches to tiling and panelling of doubly-curved surfaces, the sizing of the loops was proportionate to local surface curvatures such that smaller loops were found in the highest curvature areas. The overall structure assumed its configuration through interrelationships between support points, patterns of loops and loop materials (Fig. 06). The capability to realise complex computational geometry with physical materials is increasingly common, but still exciting. In this case, the physical structure was assembled to match the computer model's topology and, roughly, the source model's surface areas, but did not attempt to replicate its surface curvatures.

Techniques for approximating such curvatures, for example through simplification, through integration of material performance into constraints of a parametric model or through simulations of physics are becoming more widespread, even if the capabilities remain limited in cases that cannot be easily described by mathematics or are too complex to compute.

By contrast, possibilities for amorphous, soft, deformable shapes – so common in natural structures – remain under-explored. Such forms do not depend on fixed spatial positions and, therefore, can be more readily stretched, extended, ablated, fused, grafted or patched. Can abandonment of projection as extension lead to innovative structures linked to and motivated by desirable environmental processes?

1.2 Mutation

The apparent non-causality that appears in the introduction of these singularities is a consequence of the projection of the space-time onto the plane.

– Jerry B. Griffiths
Colliding Plane Waves in General Relativity, 1991

Projection can mean an actual or apparent transmutation of one thing into another. This meaning refers to purposively operated procedures requiring knowledge and craftsmanship but not necessarily a fully predictable outcome. Such projections can be understood as representations but their value can be found not only in the resulting alternative descriptions but also in the discoveries enabled by the processes of transformation, conversion and mapping.

Among such processes of mutation are workflows using subdivision surfaces. These piecewise linear polygonal meshes support modelling of topologically complex curvilinear forms using recursive subdivision and smoothing of coarse source meshes (Fig. 02). Within this workflow, simple base meshes project into exponentially increasing complexities that are only limited by the memory and processing power of available hardware.

To illustrate, the designing of CT_mesh occurred simultaneously at three levels of complexity, or at subdivision depths 0, 1, and 3 (Fig. 02). All modelling work was done at level 0. The simple geometry of this base mesh consisted of 84 polygons (Fig. 02, the outer enclosing mesh). It was achieved through a series of straightforward face extrusions from a box primitive. The resulting mesh was easy and quick to develop and adjust. A representation of the physical outcome was provided by the densest level 3 subdivision, with NURBS loops procedurally inscribed into the mesh polygons to approximate the final appearance (Fig. 02, the densest mesh – the inscribed curves are not shown).

Manufacturing directly from the depth 3 information would be prohibitively complex because this mesh consisted of 5552 polygons. Therefore, the project's workflow utilised the significantly simpler – 347-polygon – but dimensionally similar depth 1 subdivision mesh as a source of templates for fabrication (Fig. 02, the inner enclosing mesh). This solution supported intuitive modelling while allowing for improvisation by specifying only major topologies and dimensions rather than fully resolved panelling patterns.

The CT_mesh project used a procedural modelling approach within a visual-dataflow programming environment because such workflows can support non-destructive management of relationships and on-demand sampling of consequences. Workflows of this type position designers within interlinked relationships between objects, functions and communication interfaces; encouraging conversation-like interactions between cultural tropes, physical forces, computational entities and other heterogeneous agencies.

In the case of a small and abstract project like CT_mesh, this messy pluralism is undoubtedly easier than in tight goal-directed projects of the commercial world, but the point here is that all projects can benefit from flexible adaptation to multiple influences at the expense of preconceived objectives or ideas.

For example, mechanisms for on-demand recasting of data into a broad variety of forms supports opportunistic team-making, allowing integration of disparate levels of skills, co-presence of multiple high- and low-tech technologies, simultaneous deployment of heterogeneous management styles and in-parallel utilisation of multiple versions of fabrication procedures. This attitude to designing and making depends on the standardised computational recipes mentioned above but uses them in support of diversity, achieving modes of production similar to those known in other fields as just-in-time, lean or agile development. In complex settings, designers struggle to set long-term goals without receiving ongoing feedback and seeing progressive prototypes.

Recasting the project's content into multiple forms and embracing the unavoidable mutations that accompany this recasting makes for an inclusive creative environment where various skills, leadership styles and ad-hoc participation can be more readily accommodated. Visible outcomes of this pluralism are design representations and instructions that are produced on-demand, by multiple participants and in many forms: printouts; model views on screens of laptops or as room-size projections; hand-drawn diagrams, lists and schedules; hand-written notes; conversations; demonstrations of assembly sub-sequences; prototypes of detailing, geometry types or of anything that is vague; parts of completed models; step-by-step instructions ... and so on.

Fig 03. Cable-tie loop structures. Seams and transitions between improvised nesting patterns.

1.3 Prediction

And there you were, offering me your projections about the future.

– Gloria Naylor, *Mama Day*, 1988

Projection can mean forecasting, or dealing with the future. But is predicting the future even possible when we can only understand it if we look at it as if it has already happened, as if it is in the past?

The fabrication workflow developed for the CT_mesh project involved unfolding the 3D structure into flat strips, printing the template patterns on paper (Fig. 04), and using them as guides for the cable-tie loops. The unfolded template-patterns were produced through a combination of manual control and automation. The patterns were generated to be easily recognisable by builders and to be nestable within standard paper sheets. The templates were printed three-per-sheet in red, green and blue to minimise waste. The assembly was challenging because partially built components were hard to recognise and match, despite careful naming. To compensate for human error, the digital model was continuously projected onto a wall in the assembly space, a printout that included an image of the component in question in 3D and 2D was attached to each partially assembled part and several parallel registers recorded the work already done. This struggle for coherence, the intention to realise in the physical, habitable future the virtual prediction of a digital model was deliberately undermined by an approach that integrated local disruptions into continuously differentiated patterning (Figs. 01 and 03).

Fig 04. Paper templates and cable-tie loops. Note contrasting densities and nesting of loops into unfolded polygons.

Instead of attempting to match the loop distributions precisely, the assembly workflow allowed for improvisational pattern-making. Assembly was undertaken by many people simultaneously, extending from several locations on the surface. Each maker was asked to fill a polygon provided by the level 1 subdivision mesh with 16 cable-tie loops, but their order or size was not specified. This freedom resulted in diverse local arrangements that reflected individual improvisations influenced by personalities, patterns of thinking, habits, boredom or the convenience of individual builders. This loss of control, and with it the erosion of predictability, can be seen as detrimental, or as insignificant and therefore pragmatically acceptable. On the other hand, it can also be seen as an opportunity for multi-level adaptation, nuanced expression and surprise.

These opportunities for nesting of disparate processes, intelligence or influences seem particularly intriguing given the theoretical unpredictability of complex dynamic systems. Where designers interfere with the long-term management of ecosystems, continuous sampling and readjustment come to the foreground. Existing workflows such as parametric and generative modelling coupled with prototyping of material performances and assembly sequences already extend the concept of prediction into that of time travel that blurs past and future. Can guided improvisation that welcomes imprecision, difference and surprise open designing and making to a broadened range of contributors, from non-experts to animals and from simple self-guided bots to large intelligent systems of continuous monitoring and response?

Fig. 05. Interior. Despite its typologically invariable building units (loops), CT_mesh rewards exploration with a broad variety of visual events.

1.4 Delusion

The man I saw before, he was only a projection – I see that now – of something that I wanted.

– Thomas Stearns Eliot
The Cocktail Party, 1950

Projection can mean delusion, a psychological effect, a failure to apply reason and a tendency to judge external reality in terms of one's self. Thus, it is still common to presume that architectural ideas are generated, or dreamed, within a mind of a designer. Even when designing in reference to the environmental context is established as an explicit goal, abandonment of self-referentiality is difficult. For example, biophilic arguments suggest that exposure to nature can improve health and wellbeing, psychologically and physiologically. In artificial settings this leads to recommendations to mimic natural patterns.⁶

This is not only the case where the new sets out to mimic the old – and the natural patterns approved by biophilia belong to the times when humans first evolved as species – but also an example of a self-centred, anthropocentric logic that seeks to reverse the flow of evolution and reconstruct a particular human-friendly environment from an organism that adapted to it in the past but is now thought of as fixed. Such biophilia refers to the way past environments are expressed in human bodies or human preferences and can, therefore, be characterised as narcissistic ... and delusional.

The concepts of artificial/synthetic and natural/organic are well established and intuitive. The general public, press and designers all use them to describe and critique architectural environments. And yet, recent developments in such diverse fields as biology, artificial intelligence, cognition and sociology have led to the dissolution of their contrasting meanings. In the light of these changes, an up-to-date understanding of “nature” seems of particular importance in architecture because this discipline is implicated in modifying “natural” environments with “artificial” interferences. The advance of generative techniques and automated fabrication extends capabilities for simulation and management of complex processes that are often claimed to be inspired by natural systems. In this context, it is important to know what is being mimicked in biomimicry.

When CT_mesh creates perceptual characteristics of an “organic” surface (Figs. 01 and 06), does it learn from nature or engage in a case of projection by materialising human stereotypes?

1.5 Magic

I endeavoured to make him accept of three Phials, the first filled with the Elixir Salutis, the second with Powder of Projection, and the last with Potable Gold.

– Cyrano de Bergerac
A Voyage from the Moon, 1754

Finally, projection can mean a hard-to-believe, magical or legendary feat such as using powdered philosopher's stone to transmute molten metals into gold. In design, an example of magic is a sensation experienced in the presence of a hidden mechanism producing unexpected results. Thus, magic is to do with the lack of control, expressed as incomplete knowledge, overwhelming complexity, processes of emergence or effects of unobvious interactions. Can we say that wonder and delight associated with magic are a function of personal or collective ignorance? Almost 60 years ago, Arthur C. Clarke suggested that all sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic.⁷ This is particularly suggestive in a time when most readily useable technologies are beyond complete understanding of any one individual, and where the development of technologies outstrips the learning capabilities of individual humans (for example, architects – students or otherwise).

Robin Collingwood argued that magic is not erroneous science but a practice aiming to generate emotions considered useful for the work of living.⁸ This idea of magic as special utility can be taken further as imaginative experimentation within arenas of play, or magic circles.⁹ This interpretation casts the unavoidable ignorance associated with explorations of possible futures as a transformative projection of creative forces into prototypical objects, behaviours, experiences, concepts and worlds.

In line with the above, CT_mesh can be seen as a magical act that provides experiential access both to the becoming of biologically inspired structures and to their being as objects. Subsuming the idea of design fictions, this view sees architectural projects as materialised tendencies realised in support of speculative and yet tangible imagination.¹⁰ While staging of imaginaries can be helpful, the priests or curses that come with magic are less appealing. How can design mastery be cultivated without full knowledge and full control? The answers might be radically different but the question is only likely to gain in importance.

2 Reflections

[S]ome of the utterances pilloried are manifestly true; they have to be said at certain times, being in themselves neither fatuous nor tautological. What damns them is the fact that they are the only thing ever said on the subject by the middling sensual man.

– Jacques Barzun

Introduction to Dictionary of Accepted Terms, 1967

The purpose of the above sections was to use a particular project as a device for exposing unusual ways of thinking about architectural design and its technology. They are intended as open questions or triggers for imaginative reflection. Questions cannot remain open in the presence of a conclusion but to indicate possible implications this section extends the polysemy of projection with two reflections.

2.1 Potential for Surprise

The designer's role is to provide results in the form of an expected unexpected outcome.

– Nelson and Stolterman

The Design Way: Intentional Change in an Unpredictable World, 2012

The interest in surprise (improvisation, spontaneity, change) has interesting precedents across several fields. In music, the “sound of surprise” has been associated with jazz.¹¹ In broader practice, the “culture of spontaneity” that emerged in the US in the 40s and 50s and included Black Mountain and beat poets, bebop musicians, abstract expressionists, modern dance, installation art and process writing has been interpreted as a way of resisting corporate neoliberalism’s for-profit rationalities.¹²

It is not clear if the culture of spontaneity was successful in this mission because its achievements tend to become incorporated into the commercial mainstream.¹³

In architecture, an interest in the unexpected can be traced in a variety of subfields. For example, Jencks declares that criteria for architecture should include: a) representation of the cosmogenic truth of self-organisation, or emergence; b) organisational depth, multivalence, complexity and the phenomena at the edge of chaos; and c) the celebration of diversity, for example through the use of bottom-up systems able to maximise difference.¹⁴ Similarly, Gage discusses architecture of surprise as a pursuit that is informed by systems theory and its non-trivial machines.¹⁵ These examples emphasise creative processes rather than products and highlight that design is as much an exploration as it is logical problem solving. McCarthy and Wright argue that “[i]n contrast with rationalism, practice leans toward the material, practical, particular circumstances for its discourses about technology, creating potential for surprise and imagination and opening up aspects of experience not even imagined *a priori* and which would be excluded by an *a priori* model such as an information-processing model.”¹⁶

When practice is open to surprise, spontaneity and improvisation, technology can interpret, delight and inspire in addition to providing efficiency, evidence or flexibility. Because improvisational practice pursues broader goals, it imposes different creative constraints.

Left:

Fig 06. A fragment view of the CT_mesh structure. Relate to Fig. 01 and observe the emergence of proto-architectural gestures (openings, connections, volumes and enclosures) from one continuous surface.

For example, in music, improvisation implies creating within the constraints of sound rather than within the constraints of a musical notation. Similarly, in architecture, improvisation, such as that used in CT_mesh, allows working within constraints of topology or material rather than within constraints of orthographic projections.

Intuitively, improvisation is understood as a spontaneous act, while composition is planned. However, in practice differences between predetermined performance and improvisation are often of degree, not kind. The complexity of creative production and perception cannot be explained via this binary. A degree of improvisation is always present in design's core responsibility of dealing with wicked problems. In such problems, resources for a complete analysis are not available, there is a disagreement about values and yet a proposal is expected. In this context, improvisation and surprise are familiar to all design as iterative, heuristic approaches, graphic thinking and so on. The integration of contemporary technologies helps to improve analysis but also introduces new wickedness. Where full mastery of the increasingly complex, specialised, team-oriented and rapidly changing tools is not possible, their use has to be exploratory, responsive and continuously adaptive.

2.2 Designing Surprise

Surprise rarely comes from groupthink.

– Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency
Driving Technological Surprise: DARPA's Mission in a Changing World, 2013

How does the deliberate loosening or tactical abandonment of control affect the role of designer, architect or craftsman and their practices?

Ascott suggests that artists, including Cage, Foss, Antheil, Kagel or Rzewski, have understood their medium – music – as a social process rather than a particular expression of a private experience.¹⁷ Within music, understood as a subset of socially organised sound, a composer's activities include selection of portions of the available sound, transformation of selected sounds and the process of returning these sounds back to the audience.

This acceptance of such social, conversational, character of making can be further extended by the admission of non-human participants. Such participants can include variously bounded, recognisable or mysterious entities: from violins to weather systems, from animals to machines and from named phenomena to nameless intensities.

This grateful attitude towards effects of interaction can be extended into thinking about processes in other domains.¹⁸ To generalise, the ability of social groups, creative communities and organisations to adapt to and benefit from change is important in an age that faces never-before-encountered circumstances, such as that of ecosystem collapse, globalisation, overpopulation etc.

On the other hand, broad participation and the tools that are designed with it in mind, are known to cause problems.¹⁹ As Ots observes, “[a]rchitects such as Will Alsop, and other blobmeisters of his ilk, are keeping things interesting. Unfortunately, most future architects will not have this luxury due to the growing popularity of integrated team design based upon discrete pragmatic parametrics, supported by a shared digital building information model or BIM. Green design by committee is unlikely to create architecture bold enough to be instant kitsch.”²⁰ The balance between control and surprise can take multiple forms and lead to new criteria for and forms of craftsmanship, mastery and virtuosity. Might they shift towards the focusing of attention as in movement improvisation?²¹ Become central to labour politics as virtuosity of the masses?²² Resist as passionate virtuosity attempting to transcend the norm,²³ or turn into poetry?²⁴ Be used to control enemies or competitors by surprising them without being surprised in return?

The practical appreciation of the potential for surprise emphasises systemic outcomes of design, the relationships it modifies and the processes it redirects. In such context, virtuosity becomes valuable as criticality, dissent or resistance.²⁵ Whether such resisting virtuosity can be enough to sustain the usefulness of human creativity in architectural design or even the architectural design as it is commonly recognised is an open question. After all, dependence on technology proves to be self-perpetuating and rapidly deepening; while the possibility of the technological singularity is still in doubt, about half of existing jobs are already at risk.²⁶

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